

EVALUATION OF THE EFFICIENCY OF A GEL CONTAINING STEM CELL PROTEINS

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It has been shown that a preparation based on stem cell debris has the ability to have a revitalizing effect on human skin cells.

Keywords: revitalization, cosmetic preparations, extracts, stem cells.

INTRODUCTION

The skin, as one of the most important human organs, has a heterogeneous structure and includes cells of two germ layers - ectoderm and mesoderm. Therefore, the approach to improving the state of this organ should be complex: to provide for the effect on the epidermis, basement membrane, dermis itself and microvessels that vascularize the latter.

Exposure directly to the epidermis is usually limited to accelerated desquamation of epidermal cells or the temporary superficial effect of moisturizers. An alternative is to target the dermal layer. At the same time, the greatest interest among the constituents of the dermis is its cellular basis - fibroblasts present in the dermis in varying degrees of maturity, especially young fibroblasts that retain the ability to divide.

The multiplicity of possible regulatory effects on these cells provides a constant search for new specific regulators of fibroblast growth, as well as a fundamentally new approach involving cellular reprogramming. In an attempt to find specific substances in the cytoplasm, embryonic genes, mi-RNA, and translation proteins from embryonic genes were examined. By trial and error, it was Shinya Yamanaka who, among more than 30 genes, managed to identify 4 genes, the expression of which achieves reprogramming of mature fibroblasts, which, however, does not exclude the participation of other components that provide an extended effect. Therefore, fibroblasts, which form the basis of the dermis, are the most suitable candidates for targeted effects of the developed cosmetic product. Since even incomplete reprogramming can restore the ability to divide fibroblasts and, thereby, give a new quality in the processes of skin regeneration [1, 2, 3].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

During the study, samples were studied:

Active - solution No. 1.

Gel base - solution No. 2.

As a control, we studied the culture of fibroblasts without adding the test solutions.

All studies were carried out in special culture blocks (clean rooms). Manipulations with cell cultures

- in zone A of the cleanroom (according to GMP), cultivation and daily microscopic control of the state of cell cultures - using an inverted microscope with a photo-documentation system Olympus SKX 41 (Olympus Europa SE & CO. KG, Japan) - in zone B.

Based on the previously obtained results, the working concentration of the asset for research was selected - 60% of the asset, 40% of deionized water.

The specific function of fibroblasts was assessed by the inclusion in macromolecules of labeled selective precursors of DNA synthesis (^{14}C -thymidine), collagen (L- ^{14}C -proline) and RNA (63H-uridine) (all Amersham Pharmacia Biotech radiopharmaceuticals). Radionuclides with an activity of 37 kBq / ml of medium were added to 150 cm² mattresses simultaneously with 0.5×10^6 fibroblasts from a secondary 18-day culture. The experiment was interrupted after three days of cultivation, fibroblasts were removed from the flasks with trypsin-Versene solution according to the standard method and counted on a Scepter 2.0 semi-automatic counter. The counting of radioactivity was carried out in an alcohol-toluene scintillator on a liquid scintillation counter (counting efficiency for carbon - 98%, for tritium - 56%). Results were expressed in becquerels per 10^6 cells.

In order to study collagen synthesis, after removal of fibroblasts with a 0.2% trypsin solution that does not damage collagen fibers, the vials were repeatedly washed to remove the labeled L-proline that was not included.

Metalloproteinase 1 activity was studied using commercial MMP Elisa Kits (Cusabio) according to the manufacturer's protocol.

Upon receipt of a cell culture from a clinically healthy donor, three clones were isolated for the cell line. Clone 1 was cultured without the addition of the test solutions. Clone 2 was cultured with the addition of a gel base solution. Clone 3 was cultured with the addition of an active solution. To characterize the viability and proliferative activity of the resulting culture, the efficiency of cultivation and seeding was assessed.

In order to study the effect of the test solutions on the proliferative activity of skin fibroblasts 24 hours after sowing cells into vials, solution No. 1 (active) or solution No. 2 (gel base) was added to the cells and incubated for another 24 hours. On the next day, the culture medium was completely replaced with a new one and the first cell count was performed. Subsequently, cell counts were repeated after 48 and 72 hours.

Statistical processing of the data obtained was carried out using the Excel program. The significance of the difference between the studied parameters was calculated using the Mann - Whitney U test (Wilcoxon - Mann - Whitney test). Differences were considered significant at $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Analysis of the primary culture revealed weak morphological heterogeneity of cells. The culture is represented by monomorphic large cells of a fusiform, process-like shape with a large nucleus and several nucleoli. Cellular contacts are weak.

The study of the morphology of the obtained clones did not reveal morphological differences in cell lines. The study of the effect of the investigated solutions on the proliferative activity of human skin fibroblasts 24 hours after sowing cells in vials showed that a change in the level of proliferation of human skin fibroblasts is observed in relation to solution No. 1 (active solution). The revealed differences are quantitative in nature - stimulation of proliferation throughout the

observation period, both in comparison with the control group, and with the group of solution No. 2 (gel base solution). The above mentioned allows us to assume that in solution No. 1 there are components that have a stimulating effect on the proliferation of human skin fibroblasts.

In order to confirm the preliminary conclusions on the obtained effects, the time of doubling of the cell population (proliferation activity) under the influence of the investigated solutions was estimated.

From the data obtained, it follows that in relation to dermal fibroblasts, solution No. 1 has a pronounced stimulating effect, manifested by an excess of the number of dividing cells in comparison with the control value up to 33%.

It should also be noted that the cells under study were in ideal conditions conducive to their active proliferation. The acceleration of proliferation against this background is unique and deserves a separate interpretation.

This allows us to hypothesize that some of the components included in the composition of the studied solution 1 (active) help cells to overcome the Hayflick barrier, having the ability to activate telomerase, causing limited revitalization, which contributes to an increase in the proliferative activity of cells.

The results obtained in the study of the effects of solution No. 1 are a clear argument in favor of the stated hypothesis (Table 1).

Table 1.
The intensity of the synthesis of macromolecules by the cells of the fibroblastic diferon after exposure to the test solutions in comparison with the control

Sample	Incorporation of ^{214}C -thymidine into cell DNA (Bq per 106 cells)	Incorporation of ^3H -uridine into RNA of cells (Bq / 106 cells)	The number of cells removed from the culture flask (106 / cm^2)
Solution 1, n = 15	71,1±1,4*	146,13±9,6*	5,7±0,2
Solution 2, n = 15	46,0±5,1	78,22±2,2	5,4±0,5
Control, n = 15	49,6±5,3	59,9±4,2	5,4±0,2

n - number of examined samples

* - statistically significant differences from the control group ($p < 0.05$).

A special place is occupied by the parameters of the synthesis of macromolecules (DNA and RNA) by fibroblasts after exposure to Solution 1. A significant increase in radioactivity indicates the inclusion of radioactive labels in macromolecules, which corresponds to an increase in the proliferative activity of cell culture.

Studies of the specific synthetic activity of cultured cells for the inclusion of radioactively labeled precursors - L- ^{14}C -proline into the synthesized collagen - showed the following results (Table 2.).

Table 2
The degree of incorporation of labeled proline into collagen macromolecules

Sample	Solution 1	Solution 2	Control
	n = 15	n = 15	n = 15
The number of cells removed from the culture flask (106 / cm^2)	5,7 ± 0,2	5,4 ± 0,5	5,4 ± 0,4
Incorporation of proline into collagen	27,7±1,1	11,22±0,9	9,1±15

The study of the effectiveness of the components of the gel on a model of cultured human fibroblasts in terms of the synthesis of metalloproteinases showed (table 3) that its amount is minimal in cell cultures exposed to Solution 1.

Thus, the developed cosmetic product is promising in terms of renewing the cellular composition of the dermal layer of the skin.

Table 3

Metalloproteinase I activity in the culture medium

Sample	Concentration of metalloproteinase-1 (ng / ml medium)
Solution 1, n=15	283,1±25,2
Solution 2, n=15	512,0±19,7
Control, n=15	541,3±17,3

n - number of examined samples

* - statistically significant differences from the control group ($p < 0.05$).

References

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